

UNIFICATION OF FIBRE/ MATRIX INTERFACIAL MEASUREMENTS WITH LASER RAMAN MICROSCOPY

Costas Galiotis^{1,2}, Alkis Paipetis² and Christian Marston³

¹*Institute of Chemical Engineering and High Temperature Processes, Foundation for Research & Technology-Hellas, Stadiou Street, Platani, P.O.Box 1414, GR-265 00, Patras, Greece.*

²*Department of Materials, Queen Mary & Westfield College, Mile End Road, London E1 4NS, UK*

³*Centre for Composite Materials, VHE 602 M/C 0241, University of Southern California, Los Angeles, California, CA 900891450, USA.*

SUMMARY

The effect of specimen geometry upon the parameters that govern the stress transfer (transfer length, interfacial shear strength, positively affected length and stress concentration factor) in a carbon fibre/ epoxy composite was examined in detail. Five frequently employed composite geometries were considered: single fibre composite coupons incorporating discontinuous and continuous carbon fibres, multi-fibre composite tapes with a controlled inter-fibre separation, four-ply unidirectional coupons, and, finally, impregnated fibre tows. The chemistry and the curing characteristics of the matrix were kept unaltered regardless of specimen geometry. All fibre stress measurements were conducted by means of laser Raman microscopy.

KEYWORDS: interface, carbon fibre, epoxy resin, Raman spectroscopy

INTRODUCTION

As is now well established, the fibre/matrix interface determines many aspects of composite performance [1]. It is therefore useful to have measurement techniques capable of quantifying the level of fibre-matrix adhesion and aid the development of well-designed interfaces. Some of the traditional techniques to assess interfacial properties have involved experiments on individual fibres. These may be either within a laminate or in specially constructed single-fibre microcomposites. Popular microcomposite tests are the fibre pull-out type of tests [2,3,4] and the fragmentation test [5,6]. Tests on laminates include the micro-indentation test [7,8] in which a single fibre is debonded from the surrounding matrix using a micro-indentor apparatus. These techniques are generally sensitive to the conditions prevailing at the fibre/ matrix interface, such as, fibre surface treatment, fibre sizing, matrix chemistry etc. but they are also affected by the local stress field [9] which is, in turn, a function of the specimen geometry, the fibre volume fraction and the fabrication conditions. Quite often the assumptions employed in these techniques for the derivation of the stress transfer parameters such as the interfacial shear

strength are erroneous [10] and cannot be used as design criteria for a given composite application.

Fig. 1- Specimen geometries investigated

Fig. 2- Remote laser Raman (ReRaM) set up

The laser Raman technique [11] allows measurement of the stress/strain characteristics in individual fibres at microscopic level and can be applied to all composites provided that the matrix is transparent and the fibres possess a high degree of crystallinity. This technique is based on the fact that the Raman wavenumbers of the atomic vibrations of commercial reinforcing fibres, such as aramid or carbon, are stress-dependent [11,12]. Thus, unique Raman wavenumber versus stress calibration curves can be produced for each fibre, which are used to convert the Raman wavenumbers obtained along an embedded fibre to values of axial stress (or strain). Furthermore, the stress-transfer profiles obtained using the Raman technique can be converted to interfacial shear stress (ISS) profiles along the length of the fibre by means of a straightforward balance of shear-to-axial forces argument [12]. This leads to a simple analytical expression between the ISS, τ_{rx} , and the gradient $d\sigma_f/dx$ of the stress transfer profiles:

$$\tau_{rx} = -\frac{r}{2} \left(\frac{d\sigma_f}{dx} \right) \quad (1)$$

where r is the radius and x distance along the length of the fibre. The ISS profiles, τ_{rx} , are derived by (a) fitting a cubic spline to the raw data, (b) calculating the derivatives $d\sigma_f/dx$ from the spline equations and, finally, (c) employing equation (1) [13].

In this paper, the effect of specimen geometry upon the parameters that govern the stress transfer efficiency of a carbon fibre/ epoxy system are measured with the technique of Laser Raman microscopy. Fig. 1 shows the range of specimen geometries investigated in this study. By examining a wide range of model geometries the link between single fibre model composites and full composites is established.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material System and Specimen Preparation.

The material system consisted of sized (MEBS) M40B-6K-40B carbon fibres supplied by Soficar¹ embedded into a two-part LY-HY 5052 Ciba-Geigy² epoxy resin [14]. The fibres were 6.6 μm in effective diameter [15] and had been surface oxidised via a commercial process. The LY/HY 50-52 resin is based on epoxy novolac and difunctional reactive diluents. The HY 50-52 hardener was based on cycloaliphatic amine with phenolic and organic acid accelerators present. The resin and hardener were mixed at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a ratio of 4:1 and degassed for 10 minutes under full vacuum.

The details of the manufacturing procedure for the single fibre model composites are given in Refs. 13 and 22. The two-dimensional microcomposite tapes consisted of regular arrays of typically 3 to a maximum 7 individual fibres of uniform interfibre distance. Details of the preparation procedure is reported elsewhere [16]. In the case of multi-fibre composites, a $0.3 \times 0.3 \text{ m}^2$ prepreg sheet was first made by filament winding and then 4-ply unidirectional composites were made by vacuum bagging. The volume fraction of the composite was measured to be approximately 50%. Further details of the preparation procedure can be found elsewhere [19].

Laser Raman Measurements Under Mechanical Stress

A remote laser Raman microprobe (ReRaM) that was designed and built in our lab [18] was employed for acquiring the Raman spectra. The system shown in Fig. 2 utilises fibre-optic cables for laser delivery and collection. As previously, the laser was focused onto the specimen to a sub-micron spot and the Raman light was focused to a SPEX 1000M monochromator and then collected by a Wright Instruments CCD. The use of the flexible fibre optic permits operation of the microprobe in horizontal, vertical and multi-angle position, thus allowing investigation of specimens of varying size and shape and under different environmental conditions. To conduct fibre stress measurements on the various specimen geometries, the stress dependence of the E_{2g} Raman vibration mode, which corresponds to the in-plane deformation of the graphite lattice [19], upon the applied tensile stress was determined first. Single fibre carbon fibres in air were loaded in tension on a 20kN screw-driven mechanical tester according to the ASTM-D3379-75 procedure [20]. The slope of the least-squares fitted straight line was found to be $3.0 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ GPa}$

¹ Soficar (Toray) Industries, France

² Ciba-Geigy, Cambridge, England, UK.

[16] and this value represents the Raman calibration factor for the conversion of Raman wavenumbers into fibre stress in all composite applications described here.

Fig. 3- Raman wavenumber shift as a function of applied tensile stress for 11 MEBS filaments

Stress Dependence of Carbon Fibre Raman Wavenumbers

Raman measurements were taken at discrete levels of applied load. As mentioned elsewhere [21], for fibres showing intense Raman activity such as Kevlar or Ultra-High Modulus Polyethylene, real time measurements can also be performed. Fig. 3 shows the results for 11 different carbon fibre specimens in air.

Fig. 4- Axial stress distribution along a 1mm discontinuous MEBS fibre at 0%, 0.4%, 0.6% and 0.8% applied strain

Fig. 5- Interfacial shear stress distribution along the discontinuous MEBS fibre for the strain levels of Fig.4

RESULTS/ DISCUSSION

Stress mapping and ISS distribution in discontinuous single fibre model composites

The variation of fibre stress along the left and right ends of a 1 mm sized discontinuous carbon fibre (MEBS) prior to fibre fracture is shown in Fig. 4 for matrix strains of 0%, 0.4%, 0.6% and 0.8%. It is seen that initially a fibre stress (Fig. 4) at 0% applied strain) of -0.5 GPa is recorded due to the thermal shrinkage of the resin during curing. This compressive stress is as a result of the combination of both thermal stresses and curing shrinkage stresses during fabrication of the model composites [24]. As can be seen in Fig. 4, the fibre stress builds up from the tip of the fibre break and reaches a maximum value at the middle of each fragment. The length required for the stress to build to its maximum in the middle of the fibre/fragment is referred as the “transfer” or “ineffective” length, δ [25]. In the case of the discontinuous fibre model composite (Fig. 4), the δ increases from approximately 100 MPa at 0.4% to 200 MPa for higher levels of applied strain.

The corresponding interfacial shear stress (ISS) (Fig. 5) distributions have been calculated for the sized discontinuous fibre (MEBS) prior to failure by means of a cubic spline regression for the stress distribution and equation (1). As shown in Fig. 5, the maximum values ISS for 0% and 0.4% applied strains are obtained at the tips of the fibre breaks as expected from shear-lag considerations [1]. For higher values of applied strain, the ISS builds from zero to a maximum value and then decays again to zero at some distance away from the ends. This effect indicates that interfacial failure, such as conical matrix cracks [13], initiate from the tip of the fibre break and propagate towards the middle of the fibre. The upper limit of the maximum ISS (approx. 35 MPa) is considered to give a good estimate of the interfacial shear strength of the system.

Fig. 6-Axial stress mapping of continuous MEBS specimens at 1.0% applied strain

Fig. 7-Interfacial shear stress distribution along the continuous MEBS fibre at 1.0% applied strain

Stress mapping and ISS distribution in continuous single fibre model composites

In a model composite containing a continuous MEBS fibre, the mechanism of stress transfer is only generated when a discontinuity, such as fibre fracture, is present. This situation is shown in Fig.6, where the stress distributions in the presence of fibre fractures is shown for 1.0% applied

strains. In all cases, the MEBS fibre stress was obtained through the Raman wavenumber shifts by careful point-by-point mapping along a 2 mm “window” of observation. As in the case of the discontinuous fibre (Fig.4), the fibre stress builds up from the tip of the fibre break and reaches a maximum value at the middle of each fragment. The exact value of “transfer” or “ineffective” length, δ , is not always easy to quantify here as the length of certain fragments is less than twice δ . In Fig.6, an approximate ineffective length of 350 μm is observed. Note that the increase of δ from approximately 200 μm (elastic region at 0.4% applied strain, Fig.4) to 350 μm is due to the unavoidable inclusion of the failure region in the overall estimation of total δ at high strains (Fig.6).

The corresponding interfacial shear stress distribution at 1.0% applied strain (Fig. 7), derived via equation (1), exhibits a small ‘knee’ on either side of the fracture point then, reaches a maximum of 26 ± 8 MPa before it decays to zero at the middle of each fragment.

Stress mapping and ISS distribution in 2D composite tapes

2-D microcomposites with varying fibre spacing (thus volume fraction) are very useful geometries for studying the effect of interfibre distance on the load redistribution to adjacent reinforcing fibres. The 2-D composite samples studied here had centre-to-centre interfibre distances of - approximately equal to fibre diameter. The results for a fractured fibre at the centre of an assembly of 3 fibres at close (6.6 μm) interfibre proximity, are given in Fig.8 for an applied strain level of 0.75%. When a single fibre fracture is observed, the stress along the fractured fibre (fibre 2), as well as its two neighbours was closely monitored. Fig. 8 shows the fibre stress profile recorded in the failed fibre 2. As can be seen, the fibre stress drops to approximately -0.5 GPa after fibre failure and builds to a maximum value of 2.5 GPa over a distance of $\delta=200$ μm .

Fig. 8- Fibre stress along failed filament 2 in a 2D microcomposite [16]

Fig. 9- Interfacial shear stress distribution along filament 2 in a 2D microcomposite [16]

The corresponding ISS (Fig. 9) has a maximum of approx. 40 MPa near the fibre break and then decays to zero on either side of the break. A representative stress distribution along the neighbouring fibre 1 is shown in Fig. 10 for adjacent fibre 1. As can be seen, the release of stress as a result of the fractured fibre (number 2) has now been transferred to the neighbouring fibres. The fibre stress in fibre 1 builds up from a far field value of about 2.5 GPa to a maximum of about 3.5 GPa at the plane of fracture. The length over which the stress increases to a maximum value is termed “positively affected length” (PAL) [23] and a value of 400 μm has

been obtained. The corresponding ISS profiles along fibre 1 is given in Fig. 11. As expected, the interfacial shear stress drops dramatically to approximately 8 MPa as one moves away from the

fractured fibre in the radial direction.
Fig. 10- Fibre stress along near neighbour fibre 1

Fig. 11-Interfacial shear stress distribution along near neighbour fibre 1

The stress-concentration factor K_q [24] at the fibre break ($\xi=0$), for the experiment presented here, can be calculated from the expression:

$$K_q = \frac{\sigma_r^{\xi=0}}{\sigma_{\text{applied}}} \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_r^{\xi=0}$ is the stress of the intact fibre at the plane of fracture ($\xi=0$) and σ_{applied} is the far-field stress. The value of K_1 ($q=1$) for fibres 1 and 3 was found to be 1.4 for 0.75% applied strain.

Fig. 12- Fibre stress along near neighbour fibre 1

Fig. 13-Interfacial shear stress distribution along near neighbour fibre 1

Stress mapping and ISS distribution in 4-ply coupons

4-ply unidirectional tensile coupons of MEBS fibres were fabricated and loaded incrementally up to fracture. The fibre stress within a ‘window’ of 7 fibres was mapped point-by-point with the laser Raman microprobe at applied composite strains of 0.4%. The centre-to-centre fibre distance in full composites is not regular and therefore exact measurements of the fibre positions along the plane of observation have been made [17]. The obtained stress profile along the fractured fibre 4 is shown in Fig. 12. As expected, the fibre stress drops to zero at the fibre fracture and then reaches a maximum on either side of the fibre break. The distance over which the stress is built

is approximately $\delta=200 \mu\text{m}$. As mentioned earlier, the interfacial shear stress distribution is obtained by differentiating the raw stress data with respect to fibre distance (equation (1)). The results showed that in the multi-fibre ply, at a composite strain of 0.4%, the ISS distribution has a maximum of 30 MPa near the fibre break and then decays to zero on either side of the fibre break (Fig. 13). Finally, it is worth mentioning that the stress is now zero at the point of fracture (Fig. 12) as there is no sufficient residual compressive fibre stress in the as-received specimen to drive the fibre to compression after failure.

Fig. 14-Axial stress mapping along fibres 3,2,1 which are adjacent to fibre 4 fracture [16]

Fig. 15- Axial stress mapping along fibres 5,6,7 which are adjacent to fibre 4 fracture [16]

In the case of the 4-ply unidirectional composite the representative stress distributions, along the adjacent fibres to the fractured filament, fibre 4, at an applied composite strain of 0.4%, are shown in Figs. 14 (fibres 3,2,1 respectively) and 15 (fibres 5,6,7 respectively). These distributions clearly verify that the release of stress as a result of fracture in fibre 4 has now been transferred to the neighbouring fibres. The stress magnification is particularly apparent in fibres 3 (Figs. 14) and 5 (Figs. 15), which are the nearest neighbours of the broken fibre. The positively affected length is approximately equal to $2\delta=400 \mu\text{m}$ for fibres 2,5 and 6 whereas for fibre 3 the PAL is difficult to be defined due to data scatter and it ranges from 350 to 400 μm . The stress concentration factor can again be calculated as a result of the load redistribution around the fibre 4 fracture (Fig. 10) using equation 2. For the 4-ply unidirectional coupon values of 1.18 and 1.11 were measured for the nearest-neighbour fibres 3 and 5 (Figs. 12 and 13) respectively. It is interesting to note that the value of stress concentration 1.18 for a single filament break in the

case of the 4-ply composite geometry is approximately the same as that recorded in a impregnated fibre tow for the same interfibre distance.

Fig. 16- Average maximum ISS from all different geometries as a function of applied strain.

The effect of specimen geometry on stress transfer characteristics

The maximum ISS observed in the MEBS filaments for all model composite geometries investigated is plotted as a function of applied matrix strain in Fig. 16. For the discontinuous single fibres (elastic region) ISS values of average 35 MPa are observed. In the case of a 2-D multifibre composite an ISS ranging from approx. 30 to 40 MPa is recorded. For the unidirectional tow and coupon specimens values of about 30 MPa are measured. For higher applied strains (continuous single fibre sample) an average ISS of approx. 25 MPa is obtained. As it becomes apparent from Fig. 14, the observed differences in the average maximum ISS depend primarily from the applied strain under which the experiment is conducted rather than the specimen geometry. For strains higher than 1% the combined effects of matrix softening and fibre/ matrix failure brings about a reduction in the ISS of the system.

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